

Electronic scientific and practical journal
**INTELLECTUALIZATION OF LOGISTICS
AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT**

#21 (2023)
October '23

WWW.SMART-SCM.ORG

ISSN 2708-3195

DOI.ORG/10.46783/SMART-SCM/2023-21

ISSN 2708-3195

Electronic scientific and practical publication in economic sciences

Electronic scientifically and practical journal “Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management” included in the list of scientific publications of Ukraine in the field of economic sciences (category "B"): **Order of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine dated October 10, 2022 No. 894 (Appendix 2)**

Field of science: Economic.

Specialties: 051 – Economics; 073 – Management

ISSN 2708-3195

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-21>

The electronic magazine is included in the international scientometric databases:
Index Copernicus, Google Scholar

Released 6 times a year

№ 21 (2023)

October 2023

Founder: Viold Limited Liability Company

Editor in Chief: Hryhorak M. Yu. – Doctor of Economics, Ass. Professor.

Deputy editors-in-chief: Koulyk V. A. – PhD (Economics), Professor.
Marchuk V. Ye. – Doctor of Tech. Sci., Ass. Professor.

Technical editor: Harmash O. M. – PhD (Economics), Ass. Professor.

Executive Secretary: Davidenko V. V. – PhD (Economics), Ass. Professor.

Members of the Editorial Board:

SWIEKATOWSKI Ryszard – Doctor of Economics, Professor (Poland);

POSTAN M. Ya. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

TRUSHKINA N. V. – PhD (Economics), Corresponding Member of the Academy;

KOLOSOK V. M. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

ILCHENKO N. B. – Doctor of Economics, Ass. Professor;

SOLOMON D. I. – Doctor of Economics, Professor (Moldova);

ALKEMA V. H. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

Henryk DŹWIGOŁ – PhD (Economics), Professor (Poland);

SUMETS O. M. – Doctor of Economics, Ass. Professor;

STRELCOVÁ Stanislava – PhD (Economics), Ass. Professor, (Slovakia);

RISTVEJ Jozef (Mr.) PhD (Economics), Professor, (Slovakia);

ZAMIAR Zenon – Doctor of Economics, Professor, (Poland);

SMERICHEVSKA S. V. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

GRITSENKO S. I. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

KARPENKO O. O. – Doctor of Economics, Professor;

PATKOVSKYI S. A. – Business practitioner.

The electronic scientific and practical journal is registered in international scientometric data bases, repositories and search engines. The main characteristic of the edition is the index of scientometric data bases, which reflects the importance and effectiveness of scientific publications using indicators such as quotation index, h-index and factor impact (the number of quotations within two years after publishing).

In 2020, the International Center for Periodicals (ISSN International Center, Paris) included the Electronic Scientific and Practical Edition "Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management" in the international register of periodicals and provided it with a numerical code of international identification: ISSN 2708-3195 (Online).

Recommended for dissemination on the Internet by the Academic Council of the Department of Logistics NAU (No. 7 of February 26, 2020). Released 6 times a year. Editions references are required. The view of the editorial board does not always coincide with that of the authors.

Electronic scientifically and practical journal "Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management" included in the list of scientific publications of Ukraine in the field of economic sciences (category "B"): **Order of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine dated October 10, 2022 No. 894 (Appendix 2)**

Field of science: Economic.

Specialties: 051 – Economics; 073 – Management

t.me/smart_scm
facebook.com/Smart.SCM.org
twitter.com/ScmSmart

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-21>

e-mail: support@smart-scm.org

тел.: (063) 593-30-41

<https://smart-scm.org>

Contents

INTRODUCTION	6
Tadeusz POPKOWSKI , Doctor of Science (Economics), Professor, Wyższa Szkoła Logistyki i Transportu we Wrocławiu (Poland), BUGAYKO D.O. Doctor of Science (Economics), Professor (Associate), Corresponding Member of the Academy of Economic Sciences of Ukraine, Vice - Director of ES International Cooperation and Education Institute, Instructor of ICAO Institute, Professor of the Logistics Department National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
THE PROCESS OF EDUCATING LOGISTICS STAFF IN CONDITIONS OF WIDESPREAD AUTOMATION	7 – 12
SMERICHEVSKYI S.F. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Marketing of National Aviation University (Ukraine), POBEREZHNA Z.M. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Economics and Business Technologies of National Aviation University (Ukraine), KOLBUSHKIN Yu.P. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, head of department, NJSC "Naftogaz of Ukraine" (Ukraine), GURA S.M. PhD in Economics, National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>FORMATION OF THE SECURITY SYSTEM AND ASSESSMENT OF THE COMPETITIVE POTENTIAL OF AIR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES</i>	13 – 21
SHCHEKHOVSKA L.F. Senior Lecturer of Logistics Department of National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>BEHAVIORAL IMPLICATIONS IN SUPPLY CHAIN RISK MANAGEMENT</i>	22 – 32
BUGAYKO D.O. Doctor of Science (Economics), Professor (Associate), Corresponding Member of the Academy of Economic Sciences of Ukraine, Vice - Director of ES International Cooperation and Education Institute, Instructor of ICAO Institute, Professor of the Logistics Department National Aviation University (Ukraine), REZNIK V. V. Postgraduate Student, National Aviation University (Ukraine)	
<i>NEW CHALLENGES FOR LOGISTICS IN THE CONDITIONS OF MILITARY OPERATIONS</i>	33 – 42
BAIDALA V.V. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Economics National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine (Ukraine), YAKYMOVSKA A. V. Postgraduate, Assistant professor of the Department of Economics National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine (Ukraine)	
<i>FEATURES OF MANAGEMENT OF ECONOMIC SECURITY OF ENTERPRISES</i>	43 – 48

VYTVYTSKA O.D. Doctor of Economics, Professor of the Department of Public Administration and Innovation Management, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences (Ukraine), **SLYVINSKA O.B.** PhD in Economics, Associate Professor of Accounting and Auditing, SE NULES of Ukraine «Brzezany Agrotechnical Institute» (Ukraine)

*CURRENT APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF THE ECONOMIC SECURITY
MANAGEMENT MECHANISM OF THE ENTERPRISE*

49 –54

KOLODYNSKYI S.B. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Management and Administration PHEI «Rauf Ablyazov East European University» (Ukraine), **STOROZHUK O.V.** Ph.D. of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the Department of Economics, Management and Commercial Activity Central Ukrainian National Technical University (Ukraine), **LOZOVA T.P.** Ph.D. of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Management and Administration PHEI «Rauf Ablyazov East European University» (Ukraine), **KALININ O.V.** Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Management Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman (Ukraine)

*STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF CORPORATE ENTERPRISES
UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF INTEGRATION PROCESSES AND DIGITALIZATION*

55 –63

UDC 005.332.4:005.336

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2023-21-2>

JEL Classification: D4, C52, M2.

Received: 05 October 2023

Smerichevskiy S.F. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Marketing of National Aviation University (Ukraine)

ORCID – 0000-0003-2102-1524

Researcher ID – I-3736-2018

Scopus author id: – 57202676948

Poberezhna Z.M. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Economics and Business Technologies of National Aviation University (Ukraine)

ORCID – 0000-0001-6245-038X

Researcher ID – T-8659-2018

Scopus author id: – 57201258305

Kolbushkin Yu.P. Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, head of department, NJSC "Naftogaz of Ukraine" (Ukraine)

ORCID – 0000-0003-3192-2385

Researcher ID –

Scopus author id: – 57202677860

Gura S.M. PhD in Economics, National Aviation University (Ukraine)

ORCID – 0000-0001-5617-5238

Researcher ID –

Scopus author id: –

FORMATION OF THE SECURITY SYSTEM AND ASSESSMENT OF THE COMPETITIVE POTENTIAL OF AIR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES

Serhii Smerichevskiy, Zarina Poberezhna, Yuriy Kolbushkin, Svitlana Gura. «*Formation of the security system and assessment of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises*». The article investigates theoretical and methodological approaches to the formation of a system for ensuring and assessing the competitive potential of air transport enterprises. The definition of the concept of "competitive potential" is generalized in the context of covering all key internal processes occurring in various functional areas of the internal environment of the enterprise. Methodical tools for creating a system to ensure the competitiveness of air transport enterprises through the development of their competitive potential is suggested. The elements of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises and competitive advantages are defined, which are divided into three categories: resource, operational, and program-strategic. The structure of a multi-level system of indicators for assessing the competitive potential of the airport is presented. A step-by-step algorithm for forming a strategy for developing the competitive potential of an air transport enterprise has been developed.

Keywords: competitiveness, competitive potential, competitive advantage, air transport enterprises, strategy of development of competitive potential, competitive products, assessment of competitive potential.

Сергій Смерічевський, Заріна Побережна, Юрій Колбушкін, Світлана Гура «Формування системи забезпечення та оцінки конкурентного потенціалу підприємств повітряного транспорту». У статті досліджено теоретико-методичні підходи до формування системи забезпечення та оцінки конкурентного потенціалу підприємств повітряного транспорту. Узагальнено визначення поняття «конкурентний потенціал» в контексті охоплення всіх ключових внутрішніх процесів, що відбуваються в різних функціональних сферах внутрішнього середовища підприємства. Запропоновано методичний інструментарій створення системи забезпечення конкурентоспроможності підприємств авіатранспортної галузі через розвиток їх конкурентного потенціалу. Визначено елементи конкурентного потенціалу підприємств повітряного транспорту та конкурентні переваги, які поділяються на три категорії: ресурсні, операційні та програмно-стратегічні. Представлено структуру багаторівневої системи показників-індикаторів оцінки конкурентного потенціалу аеропорту. Розроблено поетапний алгоритм формування стратегії розвитку конкурентного потенціалу підприємства повітряного транспорту.

Ключові слова: конкурентоспроможність, конкурентний потенціал, конкурентна перевага, підприємства повітряного транспорту, стратегія розвитку конкурентного потенціалу, конкурентоспроможна продукція, оцінка конкурентного потенціалу

Introduction. The successful functioning and strategic development of enterprises in modern conditions requires an appropriate approach to the formation of their competitive strategy, identification of competitive advantages, and this, in turn, necessitates determining the role and importance of competitive potential in the activities of an enterprise. In today's competitive environment, more attention is being paid to the development of the competitive potential of business entities. On the one hand, this is due to the fact that competitive potential is the basis for maintaining and improving the competitiveness of an enterprise in the long term. On the other hand, the competitive potential is reflected in a set of indicators that qualitatively and quantitatively characterize the enterprise's ability to develop in the market.

In the context of market transformations, the issues of forming a system for ensuring and assessing the competitive potential of air transport enterprises are of utmost importance. After all, air transport should be

considered a complex system of numerous factors, which include constantly interacting and interdependent elements that make up a single whole. The key components of the established system are air transport enterprises, domestic and international airports, separate air traffic service units, state air transport regulatory authorities, international civil aviation organizations, etc. The interaction of individual components of the air transport system with each other and with the external environment is extremely complex and, to a large extent, leads to increased competition in this sector.

That is why the study of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises is becoming an increasingly relevant scientific task, since knowledge of its main components and the level of their development will determine their further functioning in the long term.

Literature review. Most scientific works on various aspects of the concept of "competitive potential" emphasized the importance of studying the problems of its assessment and pointed out that there are

significant differences in the definition of the concept of "competitive potential", its essence, structure and correlation with other categories. Particular attention is paid to the study of competitive potential, its assessment and components in the works of such domestic authors as O. Baribina, O. Gudzynskyi, S. Sudomyr, T. Gurenko, D. Zahirniak, O. Zalunina, A. Chumasova, N. Karachyna, L. Pertsata, V. Koyuda, A. Luzhetskyi, M. Stakhova, etc. At the same time, despite the numerous developments in this area, the study of analysis, forecasting and formation of the development of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises remains insufficiently studied.

The main purpose. The aim of the study is to develop theoretical and methodological approaches to the formation of a system for ensuring and assessing the competitive potential of enterprises in modern economic conditions, which will ensure an increase in the efficiency of competitive development of air transport enterprises.

Results. The significant importance of air transport as a catalyst for global socio-economic and technological development is due to the dynamism and flexibility provided by air transport enterprises in the overall transportation system. This contributes to the branching of the system of sectoral markets for numerous types of products and the exchange of ideas, best practices and competencies between countries. Thus, the efficient operation of air transport enterprises creates a multiplier effect that ensures the development of new industries and at the same time creates the possibility of wider competitive advantages from the introduction of new technologies and high-quality products.

Increased competition in the air transport market leads to the development of effective mechanisms and increases the relevance of the use of modern adaptive management systems that will ensure the formation of competitive advantages of air transport enterprises. The factors of the external and internal environment that affect enterprises

are characterized by their multiplicity and high dynamism, so managing competitive potential is one of the main tasks of minimizing the impact of these factors [2; 6].

Theoretical studies have made it possible to assert that the definition of the category "competitive potential" has changed significantly - from defining it as a set of resources and capabilities [1; 6], "part of the overall potential" [5] to understanding competitive potential as a set of key success factors [4] and components that are innovative and adaptable [2].

To study the concept of "competitive potential", a number of common features can be identified that are inherent in most approaches [3; 7]:

1. Availability of the resource component, which is the basis for the formation of the enterprise's potential and its availability.
2. Availability of tools for transforming potential into a real competitive factor.
3. Comparative analysis of the potential of competing market participants.
4. Consideration of the impact of external factors and the related ability of the enterprise to adapt to changing market conditions.
5. Connection with the competitiveness of the enterprise.

It can be argued that the competitive potential includes a set of available natural, material, labor, financial and intangible resources, as well as the capabilities of the enterprise that allow it to function effectively in the market by increasing its competitive advantages.

The formation of competitive potential involves covering all key business processes that take place in various functional areas of the company's internal environment in comparison with the main competitors. This creates a systematic view of the enterprise, which allows to identify all the strengths and weaknesses and, on this basis, to develop a comprehensive methodology for assessing the possibilities of its long-term development [10].

A key element of the effective functioning of air transport enterprises is the

use of methodological tools, which consists in creating a system that ensures an appropriate level of competitiveness of enterprises

through the development of its competitive potential and competitiveness of products (services) as calculation parameters (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 System of ensuring the competitiveness of air transport enterprises
 Source: developed by the authors

Thus, the elements of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises and, accordingly, the competitive advantages they provide are divided into three categories: resource, operational, and programmatic and strategic. At the same time, it is the category of operational competitive advantages that directly affects the qualitative indicators of competitiveness of products (services) of the air transport enterprise, which, in turn, are divided into groups of reliability, quality and added value for consumers, as well as a group of price indicators of competitiveness of its products [8].

The competitive potential of air transport enterprises has its own characteristics and is the basis for achieving their overall competitiveness. The competitive potential of air transport enterprises means the existence of an objective possibility of maintaining or increasing competitive advantages in the long term. It also ensures the production of

competitive products (services), helps maintain or increase market share, and creates conditions for the development and improvement of their competitive position in the future [3].

The structure of the main elements of competitive potential is different for different types of air transport enterprises - airlines, airports and ground handling operators, etc. The competitive potential of an air transport enterprise can be realized through the economic influence of management and through a number of competitive advantages [5].

Competitive advantage can be defined as any exceptional value of the products of air transport enterprises that provides them with an advantage in the market [4].

It is possible to form a total value of the integrated indicator of competitiveness of an air transport enterprise equal to the sum of the values of the integrated indicator of

product competitiveness and the integrated indicator of competitive potential. This sum

should take into account the degree of realization of competitive advantages:

$$Kc = \alpha \times Kcp + (1 - \alpha) \times Kpc \quad (1)$$

where Kc - integral indicator of competitiveness of the air transport enterprise; Kcp - integral indicator of competitive potential; Kpc - integral indicator of product competitiveness of the air transport enterprise; α - weighting factor, the actual degree of realization of competitive advantages (from 0.1 to 1).

Air transport enterprises can achieve a leading position in the market if they have sustainable competitive advantages that can change depending on the cyclical fluctuations of the industry, the conditions of aviation markets and consumer requirements for products (services).

The set of competitive advantages and elements of competitive potential can be divided into three groups [2; 6]:

- resource - possession of resources of a certain quality or quantity (natural or acquired);

- operational - efficient use of available resources;

- programmatic and strategic - the development strategy of the entity (holder of competitive advantages) and the quality of its implementation.

Identification and further realization of competitive advantages on the basis of the existing competitive potential of air transport enterprises makes it possible to form a system of indicators for its assessment.

The proposed structure of a multi-level system of indicators for assessing the competitive potential of the airport is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Structure of the multilevel system of indicators for assessing the competitive potential of the airport

Groups of indicators	Partial indicators
I. Strategic indicators	
1.1. Business-model of the airport	-structure of airlines' competitive environment; - business process management system; - the system of allocation / distribution of slots by airlines; - the system of regulation and control of operators' activity.
1.2. Market potential	- potential in the field of passenger air transportation; - potential in the field of freight (multimodal) transportation; - transit / transfer potential of the airport; - dynamics of the airport's target market.
1.3. Competitive position	- the share of the airport in the total volume of transportation of the air hub; - target positioning on the market of the air hub; - presence of "direct" competitors within the strategic positioning of competitors; - the airport's investment attractiveness.
1.4. Individual competitive advantages	- loyalty of airlines and passengers to the airport; - personnel management system; - standards and technologies ("know how", resource availability, SGHA); - airport brand.

II. Operational (exploitative) indicators	
2.1. Volumes of services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number and structure of serviced flights for the target period; - passenger flow (structure and values for the target period); - cargo turnover (structure and value for the target period); - operations on ground handling (structure and values for the target period).
2.2. Airlines-partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of served airlines by strategic groups; - characteristics of serviced airlines by strategic groups; - dynamics of changes in the structure of serviced partner airlines; - the structure of restrictions on aircraft types and schedules for partner airlines.
2.3. Financial and economic indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the structure of revenues from the "aviation" activity of the airport; - the structure of revenues from "non-aviation" activities of the airport; - the structure and characteristics of the airport's main cost groups; - structure and size of operating profit for the entire period.
2.4. Airport route network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - airport route network configuration; - "width" of the airport route network (number of destinations); - "depth" of the airport route network (characteristics of flight frequencies); - the coefficient of compatibility of flights at the airport.
III. Resource indicators	
3.1. Airport and technical support services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - characteristics of the current airport service structure; - airport infrastructure characteristics; - characteristics of the operating system of dispatching; - the degree of modernization of facilities for maintenance and repair of aircraft.
3.2. Airport complex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - characteristics of terminals (number, bandwidth, class); - structure (number and configurations) of aircraft parking spaces (zones, types); - degree of modernization of terminal equipment; - characteristics of the structure between the terminal connection and parking lots.
3.3. Airport location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of airports in the city (point) of base and air hub; - population in the city (point) of base and air hub; - characteristics of the types of transport connections with the airport; - distance from the city and highways.
3.4. Download intensity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - intensity of terminal loading (passenger and cargo); - intensity of loading (use) of airfield infrastructure; - intensity of use of the dispatching system; - intensity of use of aprons and aircraft parking lots

Source: developed by the authors

In order to increase the competitiveness of transport services, it is necessary to organize and implement a nationwide innovation program aimed at increasing the investment potential of the enterprise. Introduction of innovative technologies developed on a scientific basis with the use of new knowledge, subject to compliance with

the advanced world technical market of high-tech products [11].

The competitiveness of products (services) of air transport enterprises is formed taking into account industry specifics, which is a necessary condition for the formation of competitiveness of air transport enterprises in general, and, on the other hand, is the result of managing the realization of competitive

advantages arising from its competitive potential. The characteristics used to assess the competitiveness of air transport companies' products are divided into price (air transportation tariff) and quality (onboard service, comfort of flight schedule, etc.). These characteristics determine the respective forms of competition - price and quality (non-price) [4; 6].

To develop the competitive potential of air transport enterprises, it is necessary to develop an integrated approach to managing all elements of its structure to achieve a synergistic effect. All this should be taken into account when developing a strategy for the development of competitive potential, paying attention to the internal and external

competitive capabilities of air transport enterprises, which depend on the relevant potentials that determine them.

The competitive potential of air transport enterprises is determined by its internal capabilities, strengthening its competitive position and external factors that can both facilitate and hinder the enterprise in implementing its strategy. Coordinating the development of competitive potential through internal and external opportunities requires a new approach to the formation of competitive potential strategies.

The process of forming a strategy for the development of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises consists of the stages shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Algorithm of the process of forming a strategy for developing the competitive potential of air transport enterprises

Source: developed by the authors

The external environment of air transport enterprises is studied to determine the circumstances (or trends) that may affect their

ability to fulfill their mission. The external environment includes the air transportation market, government regulation, and

competitor behavior. Typical areas of analysis include the economy, demographics, socio-cultural, political-institutional, and technological spheres [9]. Even at this stage, the study should be strategic in nature; it is necessary to identify threats and opportunities that clearly affect the main direction of development and actions of the air transport enterprise.

After determining the impact of the external environment on the enterprise, it is necessary to consider internal resources, opportunities and constraints. The key at this stage is to correlate internal resources with external threats and opportunities. The strengths of air transport enterprises should be strengthened and weaknesses eliminated. Internal legal, professional, or creative resources should also be taken into account. The first and second stages are preparatory and allow to determine the necessary conditions for developing a strategy for the development of the competitive potential of air transport enterprises.

The next step is the assessment of competitive potential, which includes the analysis of significant structural components and the determination of a comprehensive assessment based on them, taking into account the degree of importance of each of them.

Based on a quantitative assessment of the relevant structural components of competitive potential (according to the system of resource, operational, programmatic and strategic indicators), a comparative analysis of each component of competitive potential is carried out for the entire group of assessment indicators under study and their dynamics is analyzed [10].

Benchmarking of competitive potential includes studying the competitive potential of competitors and other market participants, determining its industry average value, and comparing the competitive potential assessment with the industry average. If the value of the assessment of the competitive potential of the air transport enterprise meets or exceeds the industry average, then further

expansion of its competitive potential is not required and the focus is on the realization and use of existing opportunities [4]. In a situation where the assessment of the competitive potential of the air transport enterprise under study is lower than the industry average, the question arises of increasing the competitive potential by choosing an appropriate development strategy. The selection criteria are the internal and external competitiveness of air transport enterprises.

The final stage of the process of developing a strategy for the development of competitive potential is monitoring the efficiency of the use of resources of air transport enterprises. Monitoring of competitive potential includes the collection and analysis of information, comparison of benchmark values with actual values. After monitoring the effectiveness of the use of competitive potential, it is necessary to evaluate it in order to determine how effectively the competitive potential of air transport enterprises is used and whether there is a need for its further development.

Conclusions.

Thus, in order to develop the competitive potential of air transport enterprises, it is necessary to take a comprehensive approach to the process of managing all elements of its structure in order to achieve a synergistic effect. All this should be taken into account when developing a strategy for the development of competitive potential, paying attention to the internal and external competitive capabilities of the enterprise. At the same time, the objects of evaluation when using the presented methodology can be the competitive potential of air transport enterprises, the competitiveness of its products and the competitiveness of the business system as a whole. Thus, the proposed system of indicators for assessing the competitive potential is a key tool for analyzing it and implementing a development strategy in various market segments. The study of the system of ensuring competitiveness and its elements

allows to develop and implement practical measures to strengthen the competitive

position of air transport enterprises in the market.

References

1. Barybina O.Y. The theory and genesis of the "competitive potential" category. *Naukovyy visnyk Poltavskoho universytetu ekonomiky i torhivli*. No. 1 (56). 2013. P. 147-153.
2. Gudzinsky O.D., Sudomyr S.M., Gurenko T.O. Management of the formation of the competitive potential of enterprises (theoretical-methodological aspect): monograph. Kyiv. IPK DSZU. 2010. 212 p.
3. Zahirnyak D.M., Zalunina O.M., Chumasova A.G. Ensuring the competitiveness of transport services. *Visnyk KrNU imeni Mykhayla Ostrohradskoho*. 2021. No. 1/2021 (126). P. 17-21.
4. Karachina N.P., Pertsata L.I. Competitive potential and its role in shaping the competitiveness of the enterprise. *Ekonomichnyy prostir*. 2014. No. 86. P. 164–172.
5. Koyuda V.O. Formation and use of the competitive potential of the enterprise. *Ekonomika ta upravlinnya pidpryyemstvamy*. 2019. No. 29. P. 195-204.
6. Krasnokutska N.S. The potential of the enterprise: formation and evaluation: a study guide. Kyiv. Tsentr navchalnoyi literatury. 2005. 352 p.
7. Luzhetsky A.I. Identification of the concept of "competitive potential of the enterprise" and approaches to its management. *Innovatsiyna ekonomika*. 2013. No. 8. P. 125–128.
8. Omelchak G.V. Institutional environment and the essence of the competitive potential of corporations. *Derzhava ta rehiony. Seriya: Ekonomika ta pidpryyemnytstvo*. 2013. No. 3. P. 121–125.
9. Rovenska V.V. Enterprise potential: essence, structure and general approaches to formation. *Teoretychni ta praktychni aspekty ekonomiky ta intelektualnoyi vlasnosti*. 2010. No. 23. P. 23–28.
10. Stakhova M.V. Competitive potential as a basis for the formation of the enterprise's competitiveness. *Hlobalni ta natsionalni problemy ekonomiky*. 2017. No. 16. P. 468–473.
11. Smerichevskyi, S., Mykhalchenko, O., Poberezhna, Z., Kryvovyazyuk, I. (2023). Devising a systematic approach to the implementation of innovative technologies to provide the stability of transportation enterprises. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 3 (13 (123)), 6–18.